

INFORMED CONSENT

Research title: Prevalence and factors associated with depression and anxiety in patients with chronic kidney disease

Researchers: Goicochea-Ríos E, et al

Purpose of the study: We invite you to participate in the research study entitled "*Prevalence and factors associated with depression and anxiety in patients with chronic kidney disease*," which aims to identify the factors associated with anxiety and depression in patients with chronic kidney disease. This research will be conducted by ESSALUD physicians, and the project has been approved by the Institutional Ethics Committee.

The impact of this study will provide key information on the factors that influence the prevalence of depression and anxiety, health problems that are increasingly common in the general population and among patients with chronic kidney disease. It may also facilitate the design of educational strategies that promote a rapid and effective response to these health problems, their prevention and improved care by the healthcare team.

Procedure:

If you decide to participate in the research, the following will be done: 1. A survey will be conducted to collect personal data and ask some questions necessary for the study. 2. The survey will take approximately 15 minutes to complete. The answers to the questionnaire will be coded using an identification number and will therefore be anonymous.

Voluntary participation (principle of autonomy): You may ask any questions you may have to clarify your doubts before deciding whether or not to participate, and your decision will be respected. After accepting, if you decide not to continue, you may do so without any problem.

Risk (principle of non-maleficence): There is no risk or harm in participating in this study. However, if there are questions that make you uncomfortable, you are free to answer them or not.

Benefits (principle of beneficence): The results of the survey will be reported to you after its completion, and the results of the research will be sent to the institution. You will not receive any financial or other benefits. The study will contribute to the individual health of the person and will provide information on the prevalence of depression and anxiety as well as associated factors.

Confidentiality (principle of justice): The data collected will be anonymous, without identifying the participant. We guarantee that the information you provide

will be completely confidential and will not be used for any purpose other than research. The data will remain in the custody of the principal investigator and will be deleted after a specified period.

Problems or questions: If you have any questions about the research, you can contact the principal investigator: Evelyn Goicochea Ríos on 943482442.

Consent: Having read the purposes of the research, I authorise my participation in the aforementioned research.

Participant's first and last names Researcher's first and last names

Signature(s):

Date and time: